

FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AS KEY FACTORS IN PREPARING YOUTH FOR MODERN PROFESSIONS

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Annotation. This article investigates the role of digital technologies in preparing young people for modern professions. In the era of globalization and because of rapid development in technologies, knowledge of foreign languages and skills at digital tools are becoming really essential day by day for career success. The investigation of digital technologies such as : online learning platforms, mobile applications, and artificial intelligence have significantly improved the process of learning language. These digital tools provide learners with interactive, effective, flexible and personalized learning experiences. This article emphasizes the benefits of combining foreign language education with digital skills to boost employment for youth in the global job market.

Key Words: foreign language learning, digital technologies, modern professions, youth education, online learning, artificial intelligence.

Аннотация. Данная статья исследует роль цифровых технологий в подготовке молодежи к современным профессиям. В эпоху глобализации и в связи с быстрым развитием технологий знание иностранных языков и навыки использования цифровых инструментов становятся всё более необходимыми для достижения карьерного успеха. Исследование цифровых технологий, таких как онлайн-платформы обучения, мобильные приложения и искусственный интеллект, показало, что они значительно улучшают процесс изучения языков. Эти цифровые инструменты предоставляют учащимся интерактивные, эффективные, гибкие и персонализированные возможности обучения. В статье подчеркиваются преимущества сочетания изучения иностранных языков с цифровыми навыками для повышения занятости молодежи на глобальном рынке труда.

Ключевые слова: изучение иностранных языков, цифровые технологии, современные профессии, образование молодежи, онлайн-обучение, искусственный интеллект.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola yoshlarni zamonaviy kasblarga tayyorlashda raqamli texnologiyalarning rolini o'rganadi. Globallashuv davrida va texnologiyalarning tez rivojlanishi natijasida chet tillarini bilish hamda raqamli vositalardan foydalanish ko'nikmalari kun sayin kasbiy muvaffaqiyat uchun muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Onlayn o'quv platformalari, mobil ilovalar va sun'iy intellekt kabi raqamli texnologiyalarni o'rganish til o'rganish jarayonini sezilarli darajada yaxshilaganini ko'rsatadi. Ushbu raqamli vositalar o'quvchilarga interaktiv, samarali, moslashuvchan va shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim tajribasini taqdim etadi. Maqolada yoshlarning global mehnat bozorida bandligini oshirish uchun chet tillarini o'rganish va raqamli ko'nikmalarni birlashtirishni afzalliklarita'kidlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: chet tilini o‘rganish, raqamli texnologiyalar, zamonaviy kasblar, yoshlar ta’limi, onlaynta’lim, sun’iy.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world the improvement of technology and globalization has highly influenced the requirements of labor market. Employers increasingly expect young specialists to possess not only professional knowledge but also strong communication and digital skills. Among these competencies, knowledge of foreign languages and the ability to use digital technologies play an important role. Foreign languages open many doors to employees such as: effective communication in international environments, easy access to global information resources and high proficiency can connect people with professionals from different countries. Besides that, modern technologies significantly altered the way how people learn, work, interact with others and information. New and effective chances for improving language skills and acquiring professional knowledge were created by digital resources including : online platforms, mobile applications and artificial intelligence. Therefore, the integration of foreign language education and digital technologies is considered as the crucial element in preparing youth for today’s professions. This article examines how these two factors foster the growth of competitive and highly skilled professionals.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND DISCUSSION

In the context of globalization, foreign languages are considered one of the most vital tools for personal and professional development. Nowadays, many companies cooperate with people from various countries, so employees are required to interact with partners, clients, and colleagues from different cultural and linguistic backgrounds. Therefore, proficiency in foreign languages, especially English, significantly increases employment opportunities for young people [1]. According to Crystal, English has become a global language that plays a key role in international communication and professional interaction [1].

Additionally, knowledge of foreign languages allows individuals to access a wider range of information, such as academic resources, research materials, and professional publications. Chapelle states that language learning supported by modern tools provides better access to global knowledge and improves learning outcomes [2]. A large amount of scientific and technical information is available in foreign languages, which gives language learners an advantage in education and professional development. Moreover, foreign language skills contribute to the development of communication abilities and critical thinking.

Furthermore, learning foreign languages enhances cultural awareness and helps individuals better understand traditions, values, and behaviors of people from other countries. According to Reinders and Benson, language learning in a global context also promotes intercultural competence and communication skills [3]. This ability is especially important in today’s multicultural working environment, where effective communication and mutual understanding are necessary for success. Foreign language proficiency also plays a key role in fields such as business, tourism, information technology, and education, where international cooperation is common.

Therefore, learning foreign languages is crucial for preparing young people to meet the demands of the global labor market and to become competitive specialists in their future professions.

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Digital technologies highly change how people learn foreign language. Nowadays, students can study online by utilizing their phones or computers. This makes learning flexible and efficient because learners can study regardless of time and place. Furthermore, such kind of digital tools can provide variety of materials including: educational videos, audios and interactive exercises. With the help of these resources students can understand the language better. According to Chapelle, technologies plays a vital role in improving language learning by making it more interactive and accessible [2]. In addition, digital tools enable real time communication, allowing learners to practice language skills with native speakers and teachers. For this students mostly use apps like Zoom, Imo and etc. Technologies not only can improve linguistic competence but also increases self-esteem of students in using the language in real life situations. As a result, digital technologies play a significant role in enhancing the effectiveness of language education. There are many digital tools that help students learn foreign languages. For example, mobile applications offer short lessons that focus on vocabulary and grammar. These apps are easy to use and often include games, which make learning more interesting. Godwin-Jones states that mobile applications increase student motivation and help them practice language skills regularly[3]. Another important tool is artificial intelligence. AI can give students quick feedback and help them correct their mistakes. It can also create lessons based on the student’s level. Online platforms are also useful because they allow students to join virtual classes and practice with others. These tools help students learn faster and stay motivated.

CHALLENGES

However, there are several challenges related to the use of digital technologies in education. One major issue is that not all students have access to the internet or modern digital devices. This problem, often referred to as the digital divide, creates inequality in learning opportunities and limits the effectiveness of technology-based education. According to Reinders and Benson, limited access to technological resources can prevent students from fully benefiting from digital learning environments [4].

Another important challenge is the lack of digital literacy among both students and teachers. Some learners and educators may not have sufficient skills to use digital tools effectively, which can reduce the overall quality of the learning process. As Chapelle notes, the successful integration of technology in language education requires not only access to tools but also the ability to use them appropriately [2].

In addition, excessive reliance on digital technologies may negatively affect direct communication between individuals. While online platforms provide many opportunities for interaction, they cannot fully replace face-to-face communication, which is essential for developing speaking and social skills. Therefore, it is important to find a balance between traditional teaching methods and modern digital technologies in order to achieve effective learning outcomes.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, foreign languages and digital technologies play an essential role in preparing young people for modern professions. In today’s globalized world, the ability to communicate in foreign languages and use digital tools has become a key requirement for career success. The use of technologies such as mobile applications, online platforms, and artificial intelligence has made language learning more accessible, flexible, and effective.

At the same time, it is important to consider existing challenges, such as unequal access to technology and insufficient digital skills. Educational institutions should focus on combining traditional teaching methods with modern technologies to achieve better learning outcomes.

Overall, the integration of foreign language education and digital technologies helps young people become more competitive in the global labor market and better prepared for the demands of modern professional life.

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